

Summary of ARIES WP6 APEC & iFAST WP5.2 PAF joint Brainstorming & Strategy Workshop (BSW22)

R. Assmann (DESY), C. Carli (CERN), A. Faus-Golfe (IJCLab), E. Fol (CERN), G. Franchetti (GSI & GU Frankfurt), R. Jacobsson (CERN), V. Kain (CERN), F. Kling (DESY), M.W. Krasny (LPNHE), R. Ischebeck (PSI), A. Scheinker (LANL), V. Shiltsev (FNAL), R. Tomas Garcia (CERN), F. Zimmermann (CERN)

edited by the BSW2022 workshop organisers

A. Faus-Golfe (IJCLab), G. Franchetti (GSI & GU Frankfurt), F. Zimmermann (CERN)

The ARIES WP6 APEC & iFAST WP5.2 PAF joint Brainstorming & Strategy Workshop (BSW22) from 30 March to 1 April 2022 addressed (1) present and future AI accelerator applications, and (2) beam requirements and accelerators for the dark sector. For both themes, a number of conclusions were formulated. For example, dielectric acceleration appears to be an interesting approach for dark sector searches, calling for a suitable DLA accelerator design and experimental demonstration, while Machine Learning will become a community standard, and should be used for the design optimization of future machines. An intriguing proposal was the use of the LHC based Gamma Factory for driving a subcritical reactor with integrated waste transmutation.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreements No 730871 (ARIES) and 101004730 (iFAST).

Pushing Accelerator Frontiers network kicks off post-pandemic live meetings with a Brainstorm

The ARIES WP6 APEC & iFAST WP5.2 PAF joint Brainstorming & Strategy Workshop (BSW22) was held in Valencia's Colegio Mayor Rector Peset from 30 March to 1 April 2022. This event had been tailored to re-ignite the live workshops' true spirit after the covid pandemic's restrictions. This goal was accomplished by structuring this meeting as a "brainstorm" event. Two main topics were addressed by BSW22:

- present and future AI accelerator applications
- beam requirements and accelerators for the dark sector

Because of the nature of the event, the participants had been selected in view of their diverse expertise. The number of participants had been kept limited for this workshop, extending over 3 days. The participants were: Ralph Wolfgang Assmann (DESY, DE and INFN, IT), Christian Carli (CERN, CH), Angeles Faus-Golfe (IJClab - CNRS Université Paris-Saclay, FR), Elena Fol (CERN, CH), Giuliano Franchetti (GSI - Helmholtzzentrum für Schwerionenforschung GmbH, DE), Rasmus Ischebeck (Paul Scherrer Institut, CH), Richard Jacobsson (CERN, CH), Verena Kain (CERN, CH), Felix Kling (DESY, DE), Mieczyslaw Witold Krasny (LPNHE, Sorbonne University, Paris, and CNRS, FR; and CERN, CH), Alexander Scheinker (Los Alamos National Laboratory, USA), Vladimir Shiltsev (Fermilab, USA), Rogelio Tomas Garcia (CERN, CH), and Frank Zimmermann (CERN, CH). Figure 1 shows a group photo with 12 of the participants below (Ralph Assmann and Alex Scheinker are missing). Table 1 presents the BWS22 agenda.

Figure 1: Participants of the BSW22 workshop. We may speculate that the colleagues missing in the photo either could not withstand the intensity of the discussions or simply were not informed of the photo shooting!

Table 1: The structure of the Brainstorming & Strategy Workshop.

	March 30th	March 31	April 1st
9:00	F. Zimmermann et al. iFAST welcome and intro (the three) Richard Jacobsson, CERN: Dark sector landscape - SHIP, SHIP upgrades, "eSPS" and others	Christian Carli CERN: Hybrid EDM ring and axions? Witek Krasny, LPNHE & CERN: Visions on the future requirements for physics research	Verena Kain, CERN: Overview of Machine Learning Prospects for the CERN accelerator complex Elena Fol, CERN: Machine learning applications at the LHC and for future colliders (including muons)
11:00	Coffee Break		
11:30	Witek Krasny, LPNHE & CERN: Gamma factory concepts and atomic clocks for the dark sector	Discussion: Beam requirements and accelerators for the dark sector	Richard Jacobsson CERN: Dark Sector landscape and future search strategies Frank Zimmermann, CERN: Possible ML applications for the FCC Discussion: (1) Expert systems, (2) Machine learning for dark sector
12:30	Lunch		
13:30	Felix Kling, SLAC: The Dark Sector and Searches in Forward Physics Ralph Assmann, DESY: What advanced accelerators could do and possible beam parameters for high energies Vladimir Shiltsev, FNAL: Dark sector at Fermilab and the USA	Rasmus Ischebeck, PSI: Machine learning landscape Giuliano Franchetti, GSI: Machine learning challenges Alex Scheinker, LNL: Adaptive Machine Learning for Time Dependent Effects in Accelerators Vladimir Shiltsev, FNAL: Machine learning / AI for accelerators at Fermilab and surroundings?	Discussion: Putting the pieces together
15:30	Coffee Break		
16:00	Discussion: Dark sector proposals from around the globe & Discussions	Discussion and "hd-hoc" contributions	

The first day was devoted to the dark sector. **Richard Jacobsson** discussed the motivation, physics scenarios, and some of the principal approaches for exploring the Hidden Sector. Here, the Hidden Sector refers to Any Particles engaging in Feebly (or no) Interactions (FIPs) with the Standard Model (SM) particles. Evidence for Dark Matter (DM) comes from astronomical observations, e.g., data about the Cosmic Microwave Background and the distribution of galaxies. The multi-billion-dollar question of the dark sector was unambiguously formulated: Can we have a coupling between a photon and a dark photon? The present standard model of the hidden sector does not limit the range of parameters to explore. The DM search will follow two main lines: 1) through the interpretation of invisible energy accompanied by SM signature (i.e. by detecting scattering, decay...) and assuming DM-dark boson coupling, and 2) by detecting scattering against atomic electrons and nuclei. Direct and indirect long-lived techniques require specific detector designs and massive production of γ , g/q , b , W , Z , H . Also, electron beam-dump experiments, muon colliders, and the Gamma Factory are all predicted to help unravel the mysteries of the dark sector. For colliders, pp and e^+e^- collisions, are the preferred option. Finally, a big issue remains the sensitivity, i.e., the fact that all predictions rely on the *assumption of zero background*, which may not be easily reachable (requiring studies and detailed simulations). Figure 2, from Richard Jacobsson's presentation, illustrates the difference between direct and indirect searches. For indirect searches, advanced accelerator concepts could play an important role. Figure 3 shows that the two proposed facilities SHIP and FCC-ee would cover a large portion of the DS parameter space. The remaining free space, between SHIP and FCC-ee, could be covered by distant forward detectors at colliders.

Direct search: visible decay to SM particles

"Fixed target mode setups":
 NA62++@CERN (p@400, 10¹⁸)
 HPS, APEX, DarkLight@JLAB (e@1-10)
 SHiP@CERN (p@400, 2x10²⁰),
 SeaQuest@FNAL (p@120, 10¹⁸-10²⁰)
 (LBNF@FNAL)

ATLAS, CMS, LHCb @LHC (no absorbers)
 BELLE2@sKEKB (no absorber)
 FASER@LHC
 MATHUSLA@LHC (no spectrometer)

Direct search: Scattering off atomic electrons and nuclei

"Fixed target mode setups":
 BDX@JLAB (e@11, 10²²),
 MiniBooNE@FNAL (p@8.9, 10²⁰),
 SHiP@CERN (p@400, 2x10²⁰)
 (interest for BDX-like experiments at
 LNF, Mainz (MESA),
 SLAC, Cornell...)

Indirect search: Missing energy/momentum (slow extraction/electron association)

NA64/NA64++ @CERN (e@100, 10¹²)
 LDMX@SLAC/CERN (e@4-8/16, 10¹⁴ - 10¹⁶)

Figure 2: Direct (top and center) and indirect searches (bottom) for Dark Matter, together with several existing and proposed experiments for each category indicated on the right [Richard Jacobsson].

Figure 3: DS parameter space already excluded (colored) and covered by SHiP (blue line) and FCC-ee (pink line) [Richard Jacobsson]. Specifically, the current limits and expected sensitivities of proposed accelerator-based experiments are shown for a heavy neutral lepton (HLN) with a neutrino portal as a function of the mediator's mass and the mediator-SM portal mixing matrix element $|U_\mu|^2$, plotted against the HLN mass, assuming the latter HLN mixes only with muon flavoured neutrinos. The figure is taken from the PBC report [J. Beacham et al., arXiv:1901.09966 [hep-ex].]

The landscape of the dark sector was further surveyed by **Mieczyslaw Witold Krasny** with a presentation of the Gamma Factory concepts and various beams for the dark sector searches. The infrastructure and the operation mode of the CERN accelerators allow one 1) to produce, accelerate, cool, and store beams of highly ionized atoms; 2) to excite their atomic degrees of freedom by laser photons to form high-intensity secondary beams of gamma rays; and 3) to produce plug-power-efficient diverse tertiary beams. Figure 4 illustrates the photon energies that can be obtained in the LHC according to the type of ion. Figure 5 shows how the Gamma Factory can be used for generating polarized lepton beams, e.g., of order 10^{17} polarized positrons per second, a rate not attainable with any other proposed scheme.

Figure 4: Maximum photon energy obtained from $n=1 \rightarrow 2$ atomic excitations of partially stripped ions in the LHC colliding with a laser at zero crossing angle versus the laser wavelength required, for different types of ions [Witek Krasny].

Figure 5: Polarized photons from Gamma Factory generate polarized leptons [Witek Krasny].

A research program covering a broad domain of sciences is enabled by the “Gamma Factory tools”. After a detailed presentation of the state-of-the-art of the Gamma Factory studies Witek, concluded that the Gamma Factory can create, at CERN, a variety of novel research

tools, which could open novel research opportunities in a very broad domain of basic and applied science. Several examples of such tools were presented in this talk. It is appealing that the Gamma Factory research program can be largely based on the existing CERN accelerator infrastructure – It requires “relatively” minor infrastructure investments. Importantly, the Gamma Factory has a significant potential to produce, detect and investigate the properties of the keV/MeV mass-range DM particles (if they exist). Its potential to detect DM waves of cosmic origin remains to be demonstrated. Figure 6 sketches a possible ultimate incarnation of the LHC as a versatile Gamma factory complex supporting multiple HEP applications.

Figure 6: Schematic transformation of the LHC into a Gamma-Factory-based driver of secondary beams [Witek Krasny].

To complete the survey of the Dark sector, the workshop had the presentation from **Felix Kling** “Dark Sector Searches in Forward Physics”. The starting point (Fig. 7) was: what can be done with the present LHC beam? Here, the direction is twofold: 1) searches for BSM physics and 2) neutrino measurements. The LHC Forward Physics Facility (FPF) incorporates the FASER sub-facility (Fig. 8), whose purpose is to search for light long-lived particles. This project is foreseen at the UJ12 location near ATLAS. The presentation also covered the Dark Sector landscape with a simple model with dark matter charged under $U(1)_D$. Despite the model’s simplicity, the resulting possibilities form a jungle that depends on the tuning of the theoretical parameters. The neutrino search at LHC can also be carried out by the FASER sub-facility. The FASER Pilot Detector, of suitcase-size, after only 4 weeks of exposure detected 6 neutrino candidates. FASER and SND@LHC will soon start to take data in LHC’s forward direction. Felix’s presentation concluded that the FPF is proposed to continue this tantalizing program during the entire HL-LHC era, representing a significant extension of the LHC’s physics program towards dark sectors and neutrinos.

Figure 7: Concept of distant forward detectors at the LHC sensitive to axion-like particles (ALPs) and dark matter (DM) [Felix Kling].

Figure 8: Engineering design of FASER and FASERv [Felix Kling].

Ralph Assmann discussed advanced accelerators and their applications. The present particle-physics scenarios render plasma accelerators potentially interesting tools for reaching the expected regions of discovery, and as a complement to proton storage rings and e^+e^- accelerators. Plasma accelerators are not easily implemented for practical high-energy applications, especially for demanding collider applications. Outstanding challenges include the issue of matching into, and out of, the plasma with rms beam sizes or order $1 \mu\text{m}$, for beta functions of about 1 mm. Adiabatic matching (David Whittum, 1989) is one possible approach. Another challenge is the control of the offsets between the wakefield driver (laser or beam) and the accelerated electron bunch, at the $1 \mu\text{m}$ level. A third challenge is the necessity of using short bunches (few fs duration) to minimize the beam energy spread. In addition, one must achieve synchronization stability of a few fs between the injected electron bunch and the wakefield (energy stability and spread). From Simon van der Meer stems the idea to

control the charge profile and use the effect of beam loading to compensate for the energy spread. The next big milestone is to develop and demonstrate the user readiness of a 5 GeV plasma-accelerated beam. EuPRAXIA project is the project presently underway to accomplish this goal. As of December 2021, EuPRAXIA counts 40 member institutions and 10 observer institutions, from major European and non-European countries. Together with the Einstein Telescope, in 2021 EuPRAXIA has been one of only two new entries on the important Roadmap of the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructure (ESFRI). EuPRAXIA is the only accelerator facility selected for the roadmap in the last 5 years. It also is the first plasma accelerator facility ever included. The 2021 ESFRI roadmap is presented in Fig. 9. The investment cost for EuPRAXIA is 569 M€.

Figure 9: ESFRI Roadmap 2021; projects in the areas of Physical Sciences & Engineering are indicated by red triangles [Ralph Assmann].

Intriguingly, Ralph Assmann’s talk revealed that in the Conceptual Design for EuPRAXIA the energy conversion efficiency from wall-plug to laser driver is 0.01%, attainable today. This still is a factor of a few 1000 lower than assumed for proposed colliders based on laser-driven plasma acceleration, hinting at a long road ahead for this type of acceleration scheme. Beam-driven plasma accelerators have much higher wall-plug to driver efficiencies, 58% in the case of EuPRAXIA. However, even then, the expected total energy conversion efficiency from wall-plug to the main beam is below 3%, and hence still significantly lower than for conventional accelerators. An important point about dark sector searches is that laser- and beam-driven plasma accelerators are characterized by bunch charges of order 1 nC at about 15 kHz repetition rate, whereas dielectric accelerators have much lower charges of order 1 fC (or a few 1000 electrons per bunch) at a repetition rate of order 3 GHz; see Table 2. The dielectric accelerators are an appealing option for indirect DM searches, where individual incident electrons need to be precisely tracked, as sketched in Fig. 2 bottom.

Table 2: Required parameters for a linear collider with advanced high gradient acceleration [R. Assmann]. Three published parameter cases are listed. This table is taken from the LDG report [N. Mounet (ed.), “European Strategy for Particle Physics - Accelerator R&D Roadmap”, arXiv:2201.07895 CERN-2022-001]

Parameter	Unit	PWEA	LWEA	DLA
Bunch charge	nC	1.6	0.64	4.8×10^{-6}
Number of bunches per train	-	1	1	159
Repetition rate of train	kHz	15	15	20,000
Convolutd normalized emittance ($\gamma\sqrt{\epsilon_h\epsilon_v}$)	nm-rad	592	100	0.1
Beam power at 5 GeV	kW	120	48	76
Beam power at 190 GeV	kW	4,560	1,824	2,900
Beam power at 1 TeV	kW	24,000	9,600	15,264
Relative energy spread	%		≤ 0.35	
Polarization	%		80 (for e^-)	
Efficiency wall-plug to beam (includes drivers)	%		≥ 10	
Luminosity regime (simple scaled calculation)	$10^{34}\text{cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$	1.1	1.0	1.9

From the United States, **Vladimir Shiltsev** reported an American perspective on accelerators for Dark Matter/Rare processes searches, with a focus on Fermilab and the Snowmass process. At present, the main activity is oriented towards the production of neutrino super beams to investigate neutrino oscillations. On the world scale, JPARC and Fermilab are the two primary facilities that pursue MW beams for this purpose (Fig. 10). FNAL’s Proton Improvement Plan II (PIP-II) project is on track to provide beams to DUNE/LBNF. PIP-II is to be finished by ca. 2028, and the first phase of the DUNE experiment is set to start in 2032. Several post-PIP-II opportunities are on the table for neutrino physics, Dark Matter, and muon physics. In order of costs, these opportunities are the Fermilab complex upgrade (Booster, Recycler Ring, Main Injector, target); a PIP-II energy upgrade to 1-1.2 GeV; the development of a small accumulator ring; a Booster replacement, and the construction of an 8 GeV SRF linac together with modifications to the FNAL Main Injector. At Snowmass, joint discussions of the Accelerator Frontier and Rare Processes Frontier led to a white paper on a new FNAL PIP-II Accumulator Ring (PAR). Figure 11 illustrates that PAR will be a folded ring, of 480 m length, installed in a 240 m long tunnel. It features permanent magnets (so that the beam energy is fixed at 0.8 or 1 GeV); it has a 3” aperture, and a 20-120 Hz injection/extraction rate. PAR will enable three newly proposed HEP programs at FNAL: the exploration of the dark sector’s physics, a PRISM/PRIME-type experiment, and the search for charged lepton flavor violation. Vladimir Shiltsev also reported the intriguing new proposal of a Super-Compact Dimuonium Spectroscopy Collider at Fermilab, called “DIMUS”. The existing Fermilab Accelerator Science and Technology (FAST) facility / New Muon Lab (NML) infrastructure is perfectly suitable for DIMUS, with SRF accelerators, plenty of e^- , wide/long tunnels there is the potential for of order $10^{32}\text{cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ luminosity and producing $\sim 0.5\text{M}$ dimuons per year. Vladimir Shiltsev finally put forward the basic concept of a low-emittance high-energy muon source based on plasma wakefield acceleration.

Figure 10: Fermilab and J-PARC Power Upgrades versus year [V. Shiltsev].

Figure 11: Sketch of the proposed FNAL PAR [V. Shiltsev].

The search for EDM was addressed with a presentation by **Christian Carli** on the topic of a hybrid ring optimized for the search of EDM and Axions. This ring is operated at the “magic energy” using electro-static bends without gradient (field index $m = 0$). The strong focusing “magic energy” electric ring uses magnetic quadrupoles with strength $d B_y/dx = \pm 0.1$ T/m and $k = \pm 0.0428$ m⁻² (length $LQ = 0.4$ m). Operation is foreseen with two counter-rotating beams. Thus, the quadrupole polarity would be opposite for the clockwise and counterclockwise beams. The working point $QH = 1.754$, and $QV = 0.673$ is almost identical for the two beams. Significant variations of horizontal betatron functions with periodicity four and relatively large dispersion, as shown in Fig. 12, call for the impact on intra-beam scattering to be evaluated. The tuning of the machine for both beams is delicate, concerning, e.g., closed orbit, working point, chromaticity, and 2nd order dispersion for spin coherence. Recently, a new proposal has been made for a highly periodic and symmetric EDM-ring lattice, but many systematic effects are still to be understood and evaluated. Also, intriguing proposals to search for oscillating EDM from axion coupling have been shown (Fig. 13), including a scheme where the

systematic effects are strongly mitigated. However, the statistical measurement limit should be expected to be orders of magnitudes larger than for static EDM searches. A careful assessment of different proposals is yet to be done in order to obtain realistic sensitivity estimates and choose the best one.

Figure 12: Twiss parameters over one of four periods for the CW (solid lines) and the CCW beam (dashed lines) in the “hybrid” EDM ring [C. Carli].

Figure 13: Conceptual search for oscillating EDMs [C. Carli].

A tantalizing presentation from **Witek Krasny** in the spirit of the brainstorming workshop **addressed** the “Visions for the future requirements for physics research”. The vision starts from F. Dyson: “*New directions in science are launched by new tools much more often than by new concepts. The effect of a concept-driven revolution is to explain old things in new ways. The effect of a tool-driven revolution is to discover new things that have to be explained*”. The development of new tools is driven by 3 types of questions: HEP questions, general physics questions, and urgent societal questions. **Witek Krasny** described a personal review of the present status in HEP and relevant issues: 1. Quantum Field Theory “guide-books” to discoveries at the high energy frontier have lost their predictive power; 2. The fiasco of the all-but-one, 40 years long, searches for the “predicted” new phenomena (particles) – putting often the HEP labs on the wrong track; 3. New, unorthodox research ideas and methods are becoming more and more difficult to pursue within the “community-voice-driven” large

collaborations and research centers (“scientific populism”?); 4. Precision measurements brick walls for conventional beams and research methods at the LHC (limited often by the insufficient precision of the external experimental input); 5. The clear preference for the Monte-Carlo model-driven searches over the Monte-Carlo model-independent searches; 6. “Expected result” bias – a danger to being on the false track. **Witek Krasny** advocated creating new tools and research possibilities based on the existing accelerator infrastructures (or, including their “moderate cost” extensions) at BNL and CERN. These research tools for the next scientific revolutions include 1. Electron beam and 4π detector for the Electron-Ion Collider (EIC) – studies of the QCD in its full complexity at BNL; 2. New, low-emittance beams of fully-stripped isoscalar ions for precision measurements of the EW sector at the LHC; 3. New, highly intense polarised lepton sources; 4. New, high-intensity, flavor, and CP tagged neutrino beams; 5. Partially stripped high-Z ion and nuclear isomer beams for ep collisions in the LHC, AMO physics, DM searches, and EW measurements; 6. High-intensity photon beams for searches of weakly coupled dark matter particles; 7. Beams for accelerator-driven energy sources with nuclear waste transmutation capacities (Fig. 14).

Figure 14: Physics ingredients for a new type of accelerator-driven energy source driven by the Gamma Factory photon beams (including transmutation of nuclear waste) [W. Krasny].

The second part of the BSW22 workshop was devoted to the topic of machine learning from the perspective of its application in accelerator science. **Rasmus Ischebeck** surveyed machine learning in particle accelerators. After addressing the concept of machine learning (ML) in general (Figs. 15 and 16), his presentation identified and reviewed the five main pillars for applications of this technique to accelerators: (1) safe optimization of accelerators, (2) virtual diagnostics, (3) detection of faulty diagnostics, (4) use of ML for accelerator design, and (5) use for data analysis. ML-based safe optimization of accelerator performances is routinely carried out at PSI for the SwissFEL and HIPA; also at ELETTRA similar techniques are applied (Fig. 17). The detection of faulty diagnostics is a second prominent area of application. Here, CERN is engaged with the detection of faulty beam position monitors via unsupervised learning; also at DESY similar techniques are deployed for the superconducting RF systems. In the third pillar, virtual diagnostics approaches enabled by ML predict the response of instruments; this is particularly useful for invasive instruments such as spectrometers and screens as well as for fragile instruments; it is mandatory for broken instruments. Examples were presented from SINQ, and FACET at SLAC. Another type of application of machine

learning regards the possibility of using it as a tool for simulation and prediction. This branch envisages the possibility of training neural networks on a sparse sample from high-fidelity simulations. The trained neural network can then provide quick, almost “immediate” results. Examples of ML-based accelerator designs are the optimization of the LCLS-II injector and the optimization of the dynamic aperture of SLS 2.0. At PSI and elsewhere, machine learning is also used for data analysis, including for HEP.

Figure 15: Conceptual view of Machine Learning, embedded in the larger domain of Artificial Intelligence, and with Deep Learning as a sub-branch [R. Ischebeck].

Figure 16: Relevant ML concepts and definitions [R. Ischebeck].

Figure 17: Statistical Optimization of the electron beam trajectory at the FERMI@ELETTRA undulators, tripling average FEL energy, in 8 minutes (8 iterations at 10 Hz) [R. Ischebeck].

Following this presentation, the topic of machine learning was addressed from a different and more critical angle by **Giuliano Franchetti**, who viewed an accelerator complex as a “complex system”. Here, the emphasis was on the distinction between interpolation, fitting, and generalization, given that one major goal of ML techniques is generalization. The paradigm of “learning” was, at its bone, presented as the minimization of a specific error function, through some method. It was noted that the application of ML techniques requires a clear and well-established methodology (which also recognizes the possibility of confusing outcomes even when correctly applying ML). A linear model approach was considered, along with the use of statistical techniques to execute the training. Next, nonlinear models were discussed with logistic regression (sigmoid activation function). Then the structure of the neural networks was briefly addressed. Giuliano Franchetti pointed out that the interesting territory, to which the ML techniques may offer access, sits around the topic of “feature selection and information”. This is a technique that allows reducing the number of input attributes: smaller model size and better understandability plus faster training and running times result in greater generalization. This aspect is related to the problematic issue of large dimensionality and the time dependency of the system. Further areas of application of ML in accelerators include magnet sorting for optimization of DA; advanced magnet modeling from several experimental multipole series; the cleaning of beam diagnostics data; the ML classification according to the difficulty of operation for proposed experiments; and possibly the accelerator design and design optimization using ML (Fig. 18).

How can ML be trained by a human? Is it possible asking Oide-San to produce 100K model accelerator design for ML, NN training?....)

Figure 18: Accelerator design optimization by ML may require a highly specialized approach – only experts in ML and accelerators may be able to uncover the relevant features and train a deep neural network [G. Franchetti].

The challenging question of time-dependent effects on machine learning was addressed by **Alexander Scheinker**. The goal of his study was to develop adaptive ML-based controls and virtual diagnostics for complex phase space dynamics, such as in Plasma Wakefield Acceleration. The starting point is the observation that adaptively tuned physics models are not fast enough to serve as real-time diagnostics. Alexander Scheinker’s presentation discussed the theory of neural networks with ReLU activation function. Several examples highlighted the necessity of robust machine learning techniques for time-varying systems, i.e., for systems with distribution drifts. Adaptive machine learning (AML) can provide real-time diagnostics for such time-varying systems. It is already applied for automatic longitudinal phase space control at the SLAC LCLS and the EU XFEL, and the HiRES Ultrafast Electron Diffraction at LBNL. The principal component analysis for an electron beam was carried out. At the base of the AML method, the Encoder-decoder generative CNN for nonlinear data compression allows for a low-dimensional latent space tuning. This method has been applied at FACET-II for predicting the 2D projection of a beam 6D phase space. Here, predictions from

an AML based on a convolutional neural network (CNN) were compared with experimental beam profiles; see Fig. 19. An encoder-decoder 3D convolutional neural network was also applied for coherent electron diffraction images, using an adaptive tuning for 3D shapes.

Figure 19: Predicting 2D projections of 6D phase space at FACET-II, comparing AML predictions and the measured “true” beam profiles [A. Scheinker].

A broad review of the application of machine learning and artificial intelligence at Fermilab was presented by **Vladimir Shiltsev**. In the first part of the talk, examples, and aspirations from two recent FNAL workshops on AI for accelerators were presented in the following sequence: 1. Machine learning for Linac RF Optimization and Longitudinal optimization; 2. Booster Gradient Magnet Power Supply Control; 3. “Big Data” Booster Control; 4. Orbit Alignment at PIP2IT Using Bayesian Optimization; 5. AI/ML for NuMI Target System Monitoring; 6. Real-time quench detection; 7. FAST/IOTA RF gun stabilization and optimization; 8. MI loss minimization vs MI or RR situation; 9. Stabilization of 8 GeV slow extraction from Muon-Campus ring; 10. 6D Cooling optics design with ML elements. For example, at FNAL, the use of ML greatly reduced current ripple on the Booster Gradient Magnet Power Supply, and anomaly detection with continuous learning allowed the detection of 77% of anomalous events ahead of a magnet quench (Fig. 20).

Figure 20: Anomaly detection for magnet quench prediction at FNAL [V. Shiltsev].

This presentation also addressed the limitations of MLs for truly complex systems. **Vladimir Shiltsev** discussed the question “What is complexity?” Complexity is something that we immediately recognize when we see it, but is very hard to define quantitatively; S. Lloyd developed “Measures of complexity: a non-exhaustive list” with 40 different definitions; Complexity can be roughly divided into two categories: computational/descriptive complexities, and effective/physical or structural complexities. Accelerator Complexity can be defined by the following features: (1) Complexity to design (many dissimilar systems); (2) Complexity to build (# elements, # of systems, level of each system – “standard/off-shelf, special, unique”); (3) Complexity to reach energy = “make it work” (reliability); (4) Complexity to reach performance “luminosity” – CPT theorem. The CPT Theorem for Accelerators states that $CxP=T$, with C: Complexity, P: Performance (log of luminosity), and T: Time to reach P. It is illustrated in Fig. 21.

Figure 21: Evolution of collider performance fitting accelerator CPT theorem [V. Shiltsev].

	C , years	Interval
SLC e^+e^-	1.6 ± 0.1	1989–1997
Tevatron Run II $p-\bar{p}$	2.0 ± 0.2	2002–2007
RHIC $p-p$	2.2 ± 0.3	2000–2004
HERA $p-e$	2.8 ± 0.4	1992–2005
SppS $p-\bar{p}$	3.3 ± 0.2	1982–1990
LEP e^+e^-	3.3 ± 0.3	1989–1995
ISR $p-p$	3.7 ± 0.3	1972–1982
CERN e^+e^-	4.4 ± 0.4	1984–1997

Table 3: “Complexity” of selected colliding beam facilities [V. Shiltsev].

The most complex collider to date in terms of complexity of dissimilar systems was the Tevatron, especially when operated with the TeV electron lens for beam-beam compensation. The SppS, LEP, ISR and CESR colliders were most complex in terms of speed of reaching ultimate performance with a complexity figure of $C= 3-4$; see Table 3. The most complex future collider to build includes the highest-energy hadron collider, the muon collider, and colliders based on laser/plasma wakefield acceleration.

The European efforts in applying ML to accelerators were reviewed by **Verena Kain** for the example of the CERN accelerators. The "Evian" LHC Operations Workshop in November 2021 stressed that more advanced operation control and performances are required. This demonstrates the clear motivation for exploring ML at CERN. Machine Learning at CERN has many possible applications – ranging from accelerator design to offline data analysis, etc. –, but a major goal is the application of ML and Advanced Algorithms to speed up accelerator commissioning, speed up configuration switch times, and shorten turn-around time, by stabilizing the performance in presence of certain parameter drifts through clever algorithms. ML is thought to complement classical models with “learned” models, in particular for (1) enhanced diagnostics, (2) automated processes, and (3) the push towards self-driving accelerators. At the beginning of the presentation, **Verena Kain** mentioned recent progress from Deepmind for a Tokamak control. The issues for the tokamak involve time-varying, non-linear, multi-variate control problems. In the accelerator field, a few examples from DESY experience were presented. Back at CERN, ML has already enabled speeding up the commissioning. Thanks to ML, almost 100 collimators in the LHC were correctly set up within 50 minutes – see Fig. 22.

Figure 22: Speeding up LHC collimator alignment with machine learning [V. Kain].

Another example is the alignment of the electro-static septum in the SPS, with 9 DOF addressed by the POWELL algorithm in 2018 and 2021 based on OpenAi Gym. ML allows building models from data via regression. An example is the modeling of the “Pole Face Windings” control at the PS. ML also allows for efficient use of beam time: ML guided the SPS scrubbing for LHC 25 ns beams. In addition, ML renders operations more efficient, e.g., by helping to interpret the LHC tune signal, and providing a tune estimation algorithm on BBQ spectra that does not get fooled by 50 Hz noise. The ML with SimGan yields the most stable tune estimates from among a variety of methods. ML is also being investigated for deriving

the LHC bunch-by-bunch parameters from AI tomography. Longitudinal beam parameters at injection will be obtained with ML, from a fit of longitudinal profiles and tomography. At present in the LHC this is available online only for a single bunch, and the actual procedure is too time-consuming. ML is also foreseen with variational auto-encoders for radiation hard Optical Fibre imaging, which may be used for next-generation beam profile monitors. The CERN ML development effort is directed towards making numerical optimization “plug & play”, through offering a GUI, hiding the algorithm complexity, and separating optimization problem definition from the algorithm – see Fig. 23.

Figure 23: Making CERN numerical optimization “plug & play” [V. Kain].

Reinforcement Learning (RL) is a new concept in CERN ML applications. Numerical optimization requires exploration at every deployment. With RL, after training, the exploration phase is reduced to a minimum: one single iteration in the best possible case. This is achieved by the agent learning the underlying dynamics of the problem. The key is sample efficiency and continuous action. RL is expected to play a key role in RF manipulation in the PS, and for the tune control in the LHC. In general, ML will be one of the paths to further increase the efficiency and flexibility of CERN’s accelerators. Already many successful implementations are available. ML offers a huge potential for high efficiency at low cost – i.e., ML solutions are very often inexpensive. Some challenges are still ahead (transfer learning, generalization → including more physics). The key to success is providing a framework and infrastructure: GeOFF, the Machine Learning Platform. The ML status at CERN is “work in progress”. The ML/operation team is trying to move from R&D to exploitation. Still missing at CERN is an overall AI vision for the accelerators.

Elena Fol reviewed specific ML applications at the LHC. So far ML has mainly been used for the detection of instrumentation failures; for controlling the beam and for correcting lattice imperfection. Other promising fields are the optimization and operation automation as well as virtual diagnostics development. The key elements to be considered for applying machine learning are a) Start with a narrow task, namely, e.g., the optimization of specific parameters rather than of the entire machine; b) the performance measure of the selected model, for instance, the beam size, pulse energy, etc.; c) usefulness of ML if or where no analytical solution is available, or for rapidly changing systems, especially when no direct measurements are possible. A key precondition to using ML methods is the identification of where ML can surpass traditional methods and how much effort is needed to implement a machine learning solution. Of course, it always needs to be assessed if the infrastructure for data acquisition available is appropriate and if there are sufficient resources to perform the ML training. According to the report of **Elena Fol**, the primary results achieved are that the ML-based

toolbox for optics control allows: (1) the detection of instrumentation faults, with no manual cleaning and repeated optics analysis; (2) the estimation of individual magnet errors, hence a better knowledge and control of individual optics errors (Fig. 24); (3) the de-noising of optics measurements, increasing the quality of the measurements (Fig. 25); (4) the possible reconstruction of optics observables.

Figure 24: Supervised-learning-based optics correction [E. Fol], providing an improved knowledge of quadrupole errors for both LHC beams, at every location of the ring.

Autoencoder Neural Network

Figure 25: Denoising of optics measurements using an “ANN” [E. Fol].

In addition to the already established results, new studies are currently ongoing in the following domains: a) optics corrections for High Luminosity – LHC upgrade, with particular focus on the local optics correction, and exploring the use of the Reinforcement Learning for determining correctors settings; b) exploration of more complex optics error sources such as various coupling optics errors and their correction; and, intriguingly, c) the application of ML methods for optimizing the final ionization cooling stage for a future muon collider. Here, several approaches have been used for speeding up the simulations, such as supervised ML (Fig. 26); the surrogate model and extremum seeking have been combined and a first positive impact on the cooling performance has been estimated.

Figure 26: Using a trained ML surrogate model to optimize the ionization cooling channel for a future muon collider [E. Fol].

Among the numerous uses of ML, **Richard Jacobsson** also presented an application to detector design, specifically to the muon shield optimization design for the CERN beam dump facility (BDF) search for hidden particles (SHIP) experiment. The physics case is based on 2×10^{20} protons on target and the dual detector system will search for: 1. Hidden Sector decays ("Hidden Sector detector") and 2. Neutrino physics and search for Lightweight Dark Matter recoil signatures ("SND"). A primary challenge is background suppression, which requires the optimization of geometry in terms of signal vs background – see Fig. 27.

Figure 27: Geometrical parameters entering the ML-based signal-to-background optimization for the BDF/SHIP detector [R. Jacobsson].

The optimization process includes 1. choice of a suitable working point of the detector; 2. re-optimization, which involves the shortening of the muon shield at the cost of somewhat higher muon rates; 3. respecting the CDS detector rate limitation arising from the use of emulsion film in SND. The beam-induced background flux is expected to be of the order of 10^{11} muons (>1 GeV/c) per spill of 4×10^{13} protons. The muon shield makes use of grain-oriented (GO) steel, sheets of 0.3-0.5 mm, for creating the proper shielding magnetic field. Optimization of field configuration is obtained by Machine Learning using a sample of muons simulated with PYTHIA/GEANT. Assumptions are a 1.7 T average field in core 6 magnets of 5 m length, and 10 cm space between magnetic regions. The whole setup is described by 56 parameters, and to reach an optimization a Bayesian procedure was employed. Although conceptually simple, the procedure of simulating one spill of 4×10^{13} protons requires 1 month of CPU with 1600 cores. The execution of this procedure illustrates that the Bayesian optimization does not scale well for high-dimensional problems. In addition, the computing model imposes additional constraints such as making up to 100 guesses at once (with 16 nodes, parallelizing every function evaluation). The optimization was carried out using the scikit-optimize implementation of Bayesian optimization, which allows using Gaussian processes and random forests as surrogate models. The muon sample was reduced by a factor

of ~ 40 , to 18 million beam-induced muons, speeding up the evaluation and evening out coverage of phase space. Simulated muon paths in the current shield for different energy ranges are shown in Fig. 28.

Figure 28: Typical muon paths in the optimized BDF/SHIP shield, as simulated for different energy ranges [R. Jacobsson].

At last, **Frank Zimmermann** mesmerized the audience by discussing the possibility of ML applications to FCC. The FCC integrated program is inspired by successful LEP – LHC programs at CERN. FCC-ee is a high luminosity collider for the precision study of Z, W, H, and $t\bar{t}$. This project is a low-risk technical solution, based on 60 years of e^+e^- circular collider experience. Presently FCC-ee figures of merit – cost & sustainability are very promising as the luminosity vs. capital cost is 10 kCHF per produced Higgs boson, and 10 kCHF per 5×10^6 Z bosons. FCC-ee also promises by far the highest luminosity per electrical power ratio of all proposed Higgs and electroweak factories, over the entire range of center-of-mass energies between 90 and 365 GeV. It is therefore the most sustainable and “greenest” proposal on the table; see Fig. 29.

Figure 29: Luminosity per electric power vs. center-of-mass energy for various proposed Higgs and electroweak factories, from Nature Physics 16, 402 (2020) [F. Zimmermann].

For example, the estimated electricity cost is a mere ~ 200 CHF per produced Higgs boson. The cost for the FCC stage 1, comprising the tunnel, technical infrastructure, the FCC-ee collider, and extending from about 2028 to 2060, is estimated at 10900 MCHF. The spending profile includes expenditures for technical infrastructure from 2037 to 2043 and for accelerator and experiment from 2032 to 2045. Commissioning and operation would start in the 2045–2048 time frame. The use of ML is explored in the areas of dynamic aperture & momentum acceptance optimization using particle swarm optimization (PSO). PSO is an evolutionary algorithm with both cognitive and 'social' components, originally influenced by bird flocking behavior. PSO has been employed to improve the dynamic and momentum aperture of FCC with its high number of degrees of freedom; see Fig. 30.

Figure 30: FCC-ee dynamic aperture (left) and momentum aperture (right) for reference lattice (black) and optimized lattice (blue). The area of dynamic aperture is improved by 3.1% while the area of momentum aperture is increased by 18% - From T. Tydecks in the FCC-CDR, EPJ ST 228, 261-623 (2019) [F. Zimmermann].

For FCC-ee, the number of degrees of freedom may be reduced by keeping a $-I$ transform between sextupole pairs, and additionally by maintaining the 2-periodicity (or, now, 4-periodicity) of the machine. Doing so, 294 degrees of freedom are left. This number is still out of range for brute force scanning; evolutionary algorithms like PSO are better suited to handle the optimization. The settings so obtained can be used to train an artificial neural network (NN) to predict the off-momentum dynamic aperture for different sextupole settings, as is shown in Fig. 31.

Figure 31: FCC-ee dynamic aperture predictions for different energy deviations from a trained NN model together with true values from particle tracking, for a test data set, which has been withheld from training - From T. Tydecks in the FCC-CDR, EPJ ST 228, 261-623 (2019) [F. Zimmermann].

With such a model, the optimization process can be significantly accelerated since tracking can be avoided. The talk also highlighted the mesmerizing research line pursued by EPFL to “Develop an Expert System that emulates the decision-making ability of a human expert in optics design. Use the developed tools for the design of the FCC-ee.” (A person in the audience showed a visibly shocked reaction at the thought that this expert system would be used, as had been proposed, to replace the brain of Katsunobu Oide !!).

Conclusions

On the last afternoon of the brainstorming & strategy workshop, two summaries were developed by the workshop participants: one regarding the dark sector and one for the machine learning sector. During this development, the participants had a very *turbulent discussion* on what could be the conclusion of an event so much at the edge. At the end, after several iterations and heated debates, all workshop participants unanimously agreed on the following conclusions.

Dark Sector Accelerators

- There is a need to pursue a tool-driven revolution in science.
- EIC is on the way and it will help unravel the QCD mysteries.
- SHIP, FPF, GF, and FCC-ee are promising for the dark sector - the decision on SHIP and FPF is needed within a year.
- A question: will/should there be distant forward detectors at all future high-energy colliders?!
- We recommend studies of dark sector reach for DIMUS and GF- μ source + plasma-based μ source and accelerators.
- Dielectric acceleration appears to be an interesting approach for dark sector searches; a suitable DLA accelerator design and experimental demonstration are required.
- For the EDM ring, in-depth studies including prototype ring are recommended.
- GF-driven subcritical reactor with integrated waste transmutation would allow for future autonomous (self-powered) accelerators.
- Concerning the next HEP collider, how complex can or should it be?

Machine Learning

- Machine Learning already widely contributes to the exploitation of operating accelerator facilities – dozens of successful developments at CERN, DESY, FNAL, LANL, PSI, and SLAC.
- We expect that ML will become a community standard.
- ML should be used for the design optimization of future machines.
- ML should be a standard topic in accelerator education.
- ML could be instrumental for dark sector beam performance.
- Further work is needed on time-varying systems.
- A question to explore: is there an additional benefit or are there special applications for quantum computing in the field of accelerators?
- We should seek collaborations with ML experts from other sectors.
- We recommend building a testbed for self-controlling complex accelerators.
- A final question, how far can we go? Can one day AI replace all accelerator experts?